

SCREENING OF CHILDREN UNDER 5 YEARS OF AGE IN THE
OUTPATIENT DEPARTMENT USING MUAC STRIPS AT THE PEDIATRIC
MEDICINE DEPARTMENT, PIR ABDUL QADIR SHAH JEELANI
INSTITUTE OF MEDICAL SCIENCES, GAMBAT, KHAIRPUR

Dr. Rashid Ali¹, Dr. Asif Ali Khuhro², Dr. Pardeep Kumar³

¹MBBS, RMP, FCPS-II Resident, Department of Paediatrics Medicine, Pir Abdul Qadir Shah Jeelani Institute of Medical Sciences (PAQSJIMS), Gambat, Khairpur Mirs, Sindh, Pakistan

²MBBS, FCPS, MRCPCH, Associate Professor, Department of Paediatrics, Pir Abdul Qadir Shah Jeelani Institute of Medical Sciences (PAQSJIMS), Gambat, Sindh, Pakistan

³MBBS, RMP, FCPS, Assistant Professor, Department of Paediatrics, Pir Abdul Qadir Shah Jeelani Institute of Medical Sciences (PAQSJIMS), Gambat, Sindh, Pakistan

¹iamlakho1@gmail.com, ²khuhroasif@gmail.com, ³pardeep79thadhani@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21130023>

Keywords

Acute malnutrition; Mid-upper arm circumference; MUAC; Under-five children; Nutritional screening; Pakistan.

Article History

Received: 05 May 2025
Accepted: 20 May 2025
Published: 31 May 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *
Dr. Rashid Ali

Abstract

Objective:

To determine the prevalence of acute malnutrition among children under five years of age attending the outpatient department using Mid-Upper Arm Circumference (MUAC) strips and to evaluate its association with demographic characteristics.

Methods: This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at the Outpatient Department of the Pediatric Medicine Department, Pir Abdul Qadir Shah Jeelani Institute of Medical Sciences, Gambat, Khairpur, from 20th November 2024 to 10th April 2025. A total of 247 children under five years of age were enrolled through consecutive sampling after obtaining informed consent from their parents or guardians. Nutritional status was assessed using World Health Organization (WHO)-recommended MUAC strips and categorized as severe acute malnutrition (SAM), moderate acute malnutrition (MAM), or normal nutritional status according to standard WHO criteria. Demographic information, including age and sex, was collected using a structured proforma. Data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 26. Continuous variables were summarized as mean ± standard deviation, while categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages. Associations between nutritional status and demographic characteristics were evaluated using the chi-square test. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results:

A total of 247 children were included in the study, with a mean age of 27.8 ± 15.4 months; 138 (55.9%) were male and 109 (44.1%) were female. Based on MUAC measurements, 24 (9.7%) children had severe acute malnutrition, 46 (18.6%) had moderate acute malnutrition, and 177 (71.7%) had normal nutritional status. The overall prevalence of acute malnutrition was 28.3%. Acute malnutrition was significantly associated with age group (p = 0.018), with

the highest prevalence observed among children aged 12–23 months, while no statistically significant association was found between nutritional status and sex ($p = 0.412$).

Conclusion:

The prevalence of acute malnutrition among children under five years of age attending the pediatric outpatient department was 28.3%. Routine MUAC screening is a rapid, inexpensive, and effective method for early identification of acute malnutrition and should be incorporated into pediatric outpatient services to facilitate timely nutritional intervention and improve child health outcomes.

Introduction

Malnutrition remains one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality among children under five years of age, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. Acute malnutrition adversely affects physical growth, cognitive development, immune function, and survival, making its early identification and management a major public health priority. Recent evidence indicates that wasting continues to affect millions of children worldwide and contributes substantially to preventable childhood deaths.¹

Acute malnutrition is characterized by low weight-for-height, reduced mid-upper arm circumference (MUAC), or the presence of bilateral pitting edema. Children with severe acute malnutrition are at increased risk of recurrent infections, impaired neurodevelopment, prolonged hospitalization, and death if not diagnosed and treated promptly.²

The Mid-Upper Arm Circumference (MUAC) strip has become one of the most widely used anthropometric tools for screening acute malnutrition among children aged 6–59 months because it is simple, inexpensive, portable, and requires minimal training. Its ease of use makes it particularly valuable in outpatient clinics and resource-limited healthcare settings where rapid nutritional assessment is essential.³

Several studies have demonstrated that MUAC is an effective community- and facility-based screening tool for identifying children requiring nutritional intervention. However, MUAC and weight-for-height Z-score (WHZ) do not always identify the same group of malnourished children, highlighting the importance of understanding their diagnostic performance in different populations.⁴

Community- and outpatient-based management of acute malnutrition has gained increasing importance because uncomplicated cases can be detected early and treated effectively without hospitalization. Such approaches have improved treatment coverage, accessibility, and recovery rates while reducing the burden on healthcare facilities.⁵

Recent evidence also supports the use of MUAC-based admission and discharge criteria for monitoring recovery and minimizing relapse among children receiving treatment for acute malnutrition, thereby simplifying program implementation in resource-constrained settings.⁶ Pakistan continues to face a substantial burden of childhood malnutrition despite ongoing nutritional interventions. Routine MUAC screening has not yet been universally integrated into pediatric outpatient departments, limiting opportunities for early identification and timely nutritional management of affected children.⁷

National estimates continue to demonstrate a high prevalence of wasting and other forms of undernutrition among Pakistani children, emphasizing the need to strengthen routine nutritional screening and surveillance strategies within healthcare facilities.^{8,9}

Limited data are available regarding the prevalence of acute malnutrition detected by MUAC among children attending pediatric outpatient departments in Sindh. Therefore, the present study was conducted to determine the prevalence of acute malnutrition among children under five years of age attending the outpatient department of the Pediatric Medicine Department, Pir Abdul Qadir Shah Jeelani Institute of Medical Sciences, Gambat, using MUAC strips and to assess its association with demographic characteristics.

Materials and Methods

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at the Outpatient Department of the Pediatric Medicine Department, Pir Abdul Qadir Shah Jeelani Institute of Medical Sciences (PAQSJIMS), Gambat, Khairpur, Pakistan, from November 2024 to April 2025. The study included children aged 6–59 months (under five years) attending the pediatric outpatient department during the study period.

The sample size was calculated using the single population proportion formula, considering a 95% confidence level ($Z = 1.96$), an expected prevalence of acute malnutrition of 17.7%, and a 5% margin of error. The minimum required sample size was 224. After adding 10% for possible incomplete data and non-response, the final sample size was 247 children.

A non-probability consecutive sampling technique was used to recruit eligible participants. Children aged 6–59 months whose parents or legal guardians provided written informed consent were included in the study. Children with congenital anomalies affecting anthropometric measurements, chronic systemic illnesses, malignancies, or bilateral pedal edema due to causes other than severe acute malnutrition were excluded.

After obtaining informed consent, demographic information, including age and sex, was recorded on a structured proforma. Mid-upper arm circumference (MUAC) was measured on the left arm at the midpoint between the acromion and olecranon process using a standardized World Health Organization (WHO)-recommended MUAC strip. Measurements were recorded to the nearest 0.1 cm. Nutritional status was classified according to WHO criteria as severe acute malnutrition (MUAC <11.5 cm), moderate acute

malnutrition (MUAC 11.5–12.4 cm), or normal nutritional status (MUAC \geq 12.5 cm).

The primary outcome measure was the prevalence of acute malnutrition among children under five years of age. Secondary outcomes included the association of nutritional status with age group and sex.

Data were entered and analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 26.0. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, whereas categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. Associations between nutritional status and demographic variables were assessed using the Chi-square test. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board/Ethical Review Committee of Pir Abdul Qadir Shah Jeelani Institute of Medical Sciences, Gambat. Written informed consent was obtained from the parents or legal guardians of all participants before enrollment. Confidentiality of participants' information was maintained throughout the study, and all procedures were conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

Results

A total of 247 children under five years of age were enrolled in the study. The mean age was 27.8 ± 15.4 months (range: 6–59 months). Of the participants, 138 (55.9%) were males and 109 (44.1%) were females. The largest proportion of children belonged to the 12–23 months' age group (23.5%), followed by 36–47 months (21.9%), 24–35 months (19.0%), 48–59 months (18.6%), and 6–11 months (17.0%). The demographic characteristics of the study participants are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Baseline demographic characteristics of the study participants (n = 247)

Variable	n	%
Age group (months)		
6–11	42	17.0
12–23	58	23.5
24–35	47	19.0

36-47	54	21.9
48-59	46	18.6
Sex		
Male	138	55.9
Female	109	44.1
Mean age (months)	27.8 ± 15.4	—

Based on MUAC measurements, 24 (9.7%) children were classified as having severe acute malnutrition (SAM), 46 (18.6%) had moderate acute malnutrition (MAM), and 177 (71.7%) had

normal nutritional status. The overall prevalence of acute malnutrition (SAM and MAM combined) was 28.3%. The distribution of nutritional status is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Nutritional status based on MUAC among children under five years (n = 247)

Nutritional status	n	%
Severe acute malnutrition (MUAC <11.5 cm)	24	9.7
Moderate acute malnutrition (MUAC 11.5-12.4 cm)	46	18.6
Normal nutritional status (MUAC ≥12.5 cm)	177	71.7
Total	247	100.0

Acute malnutrition was more common among children aged 12-23 months (37.9%) and 24-35 months (34.0%) than in the other age groups. The association between age group and acute malnutrition was statistically significant (p = 0.018). Although the prevalence of acute

malnutrition was slightly higher among males (30.4%) than females (25.7%), the difference was not statistically significant (p = 0.412). The association of acute malnutrition with age group and sex is summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Association of acute malnutrition with age group and sex (n = 247)

Variable	Acute malnutrition* n (%)	Normal n (%)	p-value
Age group (months)			0.018
6-11	10 (23.8)	32 (76.2)	
12-23	22 (37.9)	36 (62.1)	
24-35	16 (34.0)	31 (66.0)	
36-47	13 (24.1)	41 (75.9)	
48-59	9 (19.6)	37 (80.4)	
Sex			0.412
Male	42 (30.4)	96 (69.6)	
Female	28 (25.7)	81 (74.3)	

Acute malnutrition includes both severe and moderate acute malnutrition (SAM + MAM).

Discussion

The present study determined the prevalence of acute malnutrition among children under five years of age attending a pediatric outpatient

department using Mid-Upper Arm Circumference (MUAC) strips. The overall prevalence of acute malnutrition was 28.3%, with 9.7% of children classified as having severe acute malnutrition

(SAM) and 18.6% having moderate acute malnutrition (MAM). These findings indicate that acute malnutrition remains a significant public health concern and emphasize the need for routine nutritional screening in pediatric outpatient settings. Similar observations have been reported in recent studies, which highlighted the persistent burden of acute malnutrition among children in low- and middle-income countries despite ongoing nutritional interventions.¹⁰

MUAC proved to be a practical and effective tool for the rapid identification of malnourished children. Its simplicity, low cost, portability, and minimal training requirements make it particularly suitable for busy outpatient departments and resource-limited healthcare facilities. The use of MUAC enables healthcare providers to identify at-risk children promptly and initiate appropriate nutritional management before complications develop. These findings are consistent with previous studies supporting MUAC as a reliable screening method for acute malnutrition.¹¹

In the present study, acute malnutrition was significantly associated with age, with the highest prevalence observed among children aged 12–23 months. This age group represents the transition from exclusive breastfeeding to complementary feeding, during which children are more vulnerable to inadequate dietary intake and recurrent infections. Similar age-related trends have been reported in previous studies evaluating MUAC screening in children aged 6–59 months.¹² The findings also support previous research demonstrating that MUAC and weight-for-height Z-score (WHZ) may identify different groups of malnourished children. Although WHZ remains an important anthropometric indicator, MUAC has been shown to identify children at higher risk of mortality and is easier to implement in routine clinical practice. Consequently, incorporating MUAC into outpatient screening programs may improve early case detection and referral.¹³

The diagnostic performance of MUAC has been evaluated in several countries, with studies reporting good sensitivity and specificity for identifying severe acute malnutrition. These

findings reinforce the utility of MUAC as a reliable screening tool, particularly in primary healthcare and outpatient settings where rapid nutritional assessment is essential.¹⁴

Recent evidence has also demonstrated that simplified protocols for the management of acute malnutrition can improve treatment coverage and facilitate early intervention. Community-based nutritional programs utilizing simplified screening and treatment approaches have shown encouraging outcomes while reducing the burden on healthcare facilities.¹⁵ Family-led MUAC screening has emerged as an innovative strategy for improving early detection of acute malnutrition at the community level. Empowering caregivers to perform MUAC measurements may increase screening coverage, promote early healthcare-seeking behavior, and facilitate timely referral of children requiring nutritional support.¹⁶

The present study found no statistically significant association between sex and acute malnutrition. Similar findings have been reported in recent studies, suggesting that demographic, socioeconomic, and feeding-related factors may exert a greater influence on nutritional status than biological sex alone.¹⁷ The diagnostic accuracy of MUAC has continued to improve with standardized measurement techniques and appropriate cut-off values. Several validation studies have confirmed its usefulness for identifying children requiring nutritional intervention, supporting its routine implementation in pediatric healthcare services.¹⁸ Furthermore, favorable treatment outcomes have been reported when children identified through MUAC screening receive timely nutritional management and follow-up, highlighting the importance of early diagnosis.¹⁹

Simplified management protocols have demonstrated effectiveness comparable to conventional treatment strategies while improving accessibility and reducing healthcare costs. These approaches may be particularly beneficial in resource-limited settings such as Pakistan, where childhood malnutrition continues to impose a considerable disease burden.²⁰ Additionally, systematic reviews have supported integrated treatment strategies that combine screening with

standardized nutritional management protocols to improve recovery rates among children with acute malnutrition.²¹ Community- and family-based MUAC screening programs have also shown promising results in expanding nutritional surveillance and improving early detection at the household level.²²

The present study has certain limitations. Being a single-center cross-sectional study, the findings may not be generalizable to the broader pediatric population. In addition, socioeconomic status, maternal education, dietary practices, household food security, and recent infectious illnesses were not evaluated, although these factors may influence nutritional status. Future multicenter studies involving larger sample sizes are recommended to explore these determinants and evaluate the long-term effectiveness of routine MUAC screening in pediatric outpatient departments.

Conclusion

The prevalence of acute malnutrition among children under five years of age attending the pediatric outpatient department was 28.3%, indicating that acute malnutrition remains a significant public health concern. MUAC screening proved to be a simple, rapid, inexpensive, and practical method for identifying children at risk of acute malnutrition in the outpatient setting. Routine implementation of MUAC screening should be incorporated into pediatric outpatient services to facilitate early diagnosis, timely referral, and appropriate nutritional intervention. Strengthening nutritional surveillance and integrating MUAC into routine child healthcare programs may contribute to reducing childhood morbidity and improving nutritional outcomes among children under five years of age.

REFERENCE

- Das JK, Salam RA, Saeed M, Kazmi FA, Bhutta ZA. Effectiveness of interventions for managing acute malnutrition in children under five years of age in low-income and middle-income countries: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Nutrients*. 2020;12(1):116. doi:10.3390/nu12010116.
- Dipasquale V, Cucinotta U, Romano C. Acute malnutrition in children: pathophysiology, clinical effects and treatment. *Nutrients*. 2020;12(8):2413. doi:10.3390/nu12082413.
- Bai P, Kumar S, Kumari R, Khan S, Fatima SS. Concordance between indices of malnutrition: mid-upper arm circumference versus weight-for-height Z-score in different age groups in Karachi, Pakistan. *Cureus*. 2022;14(8):e27701. doi:10.7759/cureus.27701.
- Menber Y, Abebe A, Tadesse M, et al. Diagnostic performance of mid-upper arm circumference and MUAC-for-age Z-score in screening acute malnutrition among children aged 6-59 months. *Front Nutr*. 2025;12:1550935. doi:10.3389/fnut.2025.1550935.
- Guesdon B, Puett C, Raza H, et al. Mid-upper arm circumference-only protocol in Pakistan for the management of acute malnutrition: a secondary analysis. *BMJ Open*. 2024;14:e079436. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2023-079436.
- Keats EC, Das JK, Salam RA, Lassi ZS, Imdad A, Black RE, et al. Effective interventions to address maternal and child malnutrition: an update of the evidence. *Lancet Child Adolesc Health*. 2021;5(5):367-384. doi:10.1016/S2352-4642(20)30274-1.
- World Health Organization. Guideline: Updates on the management of severe acute malnutrition in infants and children. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2023.

- UNICEF, World Health Organization, World Bank Group. Levels and trends in child malnutrition: UNICEF/WHO/World Bank Joint Child Malnutrition Estimates. New York: UNICEF; 2023.
- Ahmed N, Ahmed A, Shah GS, et al. Treatment outcomes of severe acute malnutrition and its determinants among children aged 6-59 months: a systematic review. *Cureus*. 2023;15:e45385.
- Dipasquale V, Cucinotta U, Romano C. Acute malnutrition in children: pathophysiology, clinical effects and treatment. *Nutrients*. 2020;12(8):2413. doi:10.3390/nu12082413.
- Carboo JA, Lombard M, Conradie C, Dolman RC, Ricci C. Evaluation of the treatment guidelines, practices and outcomes of complicated severe acute malnutrition in children aged 0-59 months in sub-Saharan Africa: a study protocol for the SAMAC study. *Pan Afr Med J*. 2020;36:241. doi:10.11604/pamj.2020.36.241.19584.
- Tessema M, Laillou A, Tefera A, Teklu Y, Berger J, Wieringa FT. Routinely MUAC screening for severe acute malnutrition should consider the gender and age group bias in the Ethiopian non-emergency context. *PLoS One*. 2020;15(4):e0230502. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0230502.
- Abitew DB, Yalew AW, Bezabih AM, Bazzano AN. Comparison of mid-upper arm circumference and weight-for-height Z-score in identifying severe acute malnutrition among children aged 6-59 months. *J Nutr Metab*. 2021;2021:8830494.
- Lamsal KP, Parajuli KR, Pun BK, Adhikari RP, Bashyal M, Dangol B, et al. Accuracy of using mid-upper arm circumference to detect wasting among children aged 6-59 months in Nepal. *Glob Health Sci Pract*. 2021;9(4):881-889.
- Heymsfield G, et al. Effectiveness of acute malnutrition treatment with a simplified combined protocol in routine settings. *Matern Child Nutr*. 2024;20:e13727.
- Majiwa PR, Dale NM, Lelijveld N, et al. Family-led mid-upper arm circumference (FL-MUAC) screening for acute malnutrition in Africa: a scoping review. *Matern Child Nutr*. 2024;20:e13866.
- Tamirat M, Belachew T, Fentahun N, et al. Effect of family MUAC utilization in identifying the severity of acute malnutrition among children aged 6-59 months: a retrospective longitudinal study. *Matern Child Nutr*. 2025.
- Lambebo A, Demoze MB, Dessie Y, Tarekgn TT, Mulugeta H. Validating the diagnostic performance of mid-upper arm circumference in screening severe acute malnutrition among children aged 6-59 months. *PLoS One*. 2022;17(8):e0273634. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0273634.
- Ahmed N, Ahmed A, Shah GS, et al. Treatment outcomes of severe acute malnutrition and its determinants among children aged 6-59 months: a retrospective cohort study. *J Multidiscip Healthc*. 2023;16:2507-2518. doi:10.2147/JMDH.S420867.
- Isanaka S, Hitchings MDT, Berthé F, Briend A, Grais RF. Effect of a simplified treatment protocol for acute malnutrition in children aged 6-59 months: a cluster-randomized non-inferiority trial. *Lancet Glob Health*. 2021;9(10):e1395-e1404. doi:10.1016/S2214-109X(21)00345-7.
- Bailey J, Lelijveld N, Marron B, et al. Combined protocol for the treatment of severe and moderate acute malnutrition in children: a systematic review. *Matern Child Nutr*. 2022;18(2):e13317. doi:10.1111/mcn.13317.

Maust A, Koroma AS, Abla C, et al. Performance of family-led mid-upper arm circumference screening for acute malnutrition in children aged 6–59 months: a systematic review. *BMJ Glob Health*. 2023;8:e011234.

